

$\pi g g \zeta^*$ -CLOSED SETS AND QUASI $g \zeta^*$ -NORMAL SPACES

¹Hamant Kumar and ²Jitendra Kumar

Department of Mathematics

¹Government Degree College, Bilaspur-Rampur, 244921, U. P. (India)

²Shyamlal Sarswati Mahavidhalaya, Shikarpur-203395, U. P. (India)

Abstract: In this paper, we introduce a new class of sets called $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed sets in topological spaces. Also we study and investigate the relationship with other existing closed sets. Moreover, we introduce some functions such as $g \zeta^*$ -closed, $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed, almost $g \zeta^*$ -closed, almost $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed, $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -continuous and almost $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -continuous. We also study a new class of normal space called, quasi $g \zeta^*$ -normal space. The relationships among normal, π -normal, quasi normal, softly normal, mildly normal, α -normal, $\pi \alpha$ -normal, quasi α -normal, softly α -normal, mildly α -normal, $g \zeta^*$ -normal, $\pi g \zeta^*$ -normal, quasi $g \zeta^*$ -normal, softly $g \zeta^*$ -normal and mildly $g \zeta^*$ -normal spaces are investigated. Further we show that this property is a topological property and it is a hereditary property only with respect to closed domain subspaces. Utilizing $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed sets and some functions, we obtained some characterizations and preservation theorems for quasi $g \zeta^*$ -normal spaces.

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Keywords : π -open, $g \zeta^*$ -open, $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -open, π -closed, $g \zeta^*$ -closed, and $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed sets; $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed, almost $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed, $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -continuous and almost $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -continuous functions; quasi $g \zeta^*$ -normal spaces.

1. Introduction

In 1965, Njastad [13] introduced the concept of α -open sets in topological spaces. In 1968, the notion of quasi normal space was introduced by Zaitsev [21]. In 1970, Levine [11] initiated the study of so called generalized closed (briefly g -closed) sets in order to extend many of the most important properties of closed sets to a large family. In 1973, Singal and Singal [20] introduced the notion of mildly normal spaces in topological spaces. In 1990, Lal and Rahman [10] have further studied notions of quasi normal and mildly normal spaces. In 1994, H. Maki et al. [12] introduced the notion of αg -closed sets. In 2000, Dontchev and Noiri [4] introduced the notion of πg -closed sets and by using these sets, obtained a new characterization of quasi normal space. In 2001, A. V. Arhangel'skii and Ludwig [1] introduced the concepts of α -normal and β -normal spaces. In 2004, Nono et al. [15] introduced the notion of $g^\# \alpha$ -closed sets in topological spaces. In 2007, Arockiarani and C. Janaki [2] introduced the notion of $\pi g \alpha$ -closed sets in topological spaces and by using $\pi g \alpha$ -closed sets, obtained a new characterization of quasi α -normal spaces. In 2008, Kalantan [6] introduced a weaker version of normality called π -normality and proved that π -normality is a property which lies between normality and almost normality. In 2009, R. Devi et al. [3] introduced the notion of $g^\# \alpha$ -closed sets in topological spaces. In 2013, Kokilavani [7] introduced the notion of $g \zeta^*$ -closed sets in topological spaces and investigated some of their properties. In 2015, T. C. K. Raman [16] introduced the concepts of $\pi \alpha$ -normal spaces. In 2018, Hamant Kumar [5] introduced some normal spaces such as $g \zeta^*$ -normal, $\pi g \zeta^*$ -normal, quasi $g \zeta^*$ -normal and mildly $g \zeta^*$ -normal, and the relationships among these normal spaces are investigated.

2. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, spaces (X, \mathfrak{T}) , (Y, σ) , and (Z, γ) (or simply X , Y and Z) always mean topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. Let A be a subset of a space X . The closure of A and interior of A are denoted by $\text{cl}(A)$ and $\text{int}(A)$ respectively. A subset A is said to be **regular open** (resp. **regular closed**) if $A = \text{int}(\text{cl}(A))$ (resp. $A = \text{cl}(\text{int}(A))$). The finite union of regular open sets is said to be **π -open**. The complement of a π -open set is said to be **π -closed**. A is said to be **α -open** [13] if $A \subset \text{int}(\text{cl}(\text{int}(A)))$. The complement of a α -open set is said to be **α -closed**. The intersection of all α -closed sets containing A is called **α -closure** [13] of A , and is denoted by $\alpha\text{-cl}(A)$. The **α -interior** [13] of A , denoted by $\alpha\text{-int}(A)$, is defined as union of all α -open sets contained in A .

2.1 Definition. A subset A of a space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be

- (1) **generalized closed** (briefly **g-closed**) [11] if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{T}$.
- (2) **π g-closed** [4] if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X .
- (3) **α -generalized closed** (briefly **α g-closed**) [12] if $\alpha\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{T}$.
- (4) **$\pi\alpha$ -closed** [2] if $\alpha\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X .
- (5) **generalized $\#$ α -closed** (briefly **$g^\#\alpha$ -closed**) [15] if $\alpha\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and is g -open in X .
- (6) **$\#$ generalized α -closed** (briefly **$\#g\alpha$ -closed**) [3] if $\alpha\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is $g^\#\alpha$ -open in X .
- (7) **$g\zeta^*$ -closed** [7] if $\alpha\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is $\#g\alpha$ -open in X .
- (8) **g -open** (resp. **π g-open, α g-open, $\pi\alpha$ -open, $g^\#\alpha$ -open, $\#g\alpha$ -open, $g\zeta^*$ -open) set if the complement of A is g -closed (resp. π g-closed, α g-closed, $\pi\alpha$ -closed, $g^\#\alpha$ -closed, $\#g\alpha$ -closed, $g\zeta^*$ -closed).**

The intersection of all $g\zeta^*$ -closed sets containing A is called **$g\zeta^*$ -closure of A** , and is denoted by $g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A)$. The **$g\zeta^*$ -interior of A** , denoted by $g\zeta^*\text{-int}(A)$, is defined as union of all $g\zeta^*$ -open sets contained in A . The family of all $g\zeta^*$ -closed (resp. $g\zeta^*$ -open) sets of a space X is denoted by $g\zeta^*\text{-C}(X)$ (resp. $g\zeta^*\text{-O}(X)$).

2.2 Definition. A subset A of a space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be

- (1) **generalized $g\zeta^*$ -closed** [9] (briefly **gg ζ^* -closed**) if $g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{T}$.
- (2) **π -generalized $g\zeta^*$ -closed** (briefly **π gg ζ^* -closed**) if $g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X .

2.3 Remark. We have the following implications for the properties of subsets:

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
 \text{closed} & \Rightarrow & g\text{-closed} & \Rightarrow & \pi g\text{-closed} \\
 \Downarrow & & \Downarrow & & \Downarrow \\
 \alpha\text{-closed} & \Rightarrow & \alpha g\text{-closed} & \Rightarrow & \pi \alpha\text{-closed} \\
 \Downarrow & & \Downarrow & & \Downarrow \\
 g\zeta^*\text{-closed} & \Rightarrow & gg\zeta^*\text{-closed} & \Rightarrow & \pi gg\zeta^*\text{-closed}
 \end{array}$$

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

2.4 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{b\}$ is g -closed as well as αg -closed. Hence A is $gg\zeta^*$ -closed. But it is not closed.

2.5 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{c\}$ is $\pi g\alpha$ -closed as well as $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed but not g -closed.

2.6 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a\}$ is $\pi g\alpha$ -closed as well as $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed but not closed.

2.7 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a\}$ is α -closed as well as αg -closed. Hence A is $g\zeta^*$ -closed. But it is not closed.

2.8 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{b\}$ is αg -closed as well as $gg\zeta^*$ -closed. But it is not $g\zeta^*$ -closed.

2.9 Theorem. For $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed sets of a space X , the following properties hold:

- Every finite union of $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed sets is always a $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed set.
- Even a countable union of $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed sets need not be a $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed set.
- Even a finite intersection of $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed sets may fail to be a $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed set.

Proof.

(a) Let A and B be any two $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed sets. Therefore $g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ and $g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(B) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$, $B \subset U$ and U is π -open. Let $A \cup B \subset U$ where U is π -open.

Since, $g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A \cup B) \subset g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A) \cup g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(B) \subset U$, we have $A \cup B$ is $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed.

(b) Let R be the real line with the usual topology. Every singleton is $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed. However, $A = \{1/i : i = 2, 3, \dots\}$ is not $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed, since $A \subset (0, 1)$ which is π -open but $g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A) \not\subset (0, 1)$.

(c) Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and let $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, X\}$. Let $A = \{a, b, c\}$ and $B = \{a, b, d\}$ are $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed sets. But $A \cap B = \{a, b\} \subset \{a, b\}$ which is π -open. $g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A \cap B) \not\subset \{a, b\}$. Hence $A \cap B$ is not $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed.

2.10 Theorem: If A is $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed and $A \subset B \subset g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A)$ then B is $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed.

Proof: Since A is $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed, $g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open. Let $B \subset U$ and U is π -open. Since $B \subset g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A)$, $g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(B) \subset g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$. Hence B is $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed.

2.11 Theorem. Let A be a $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed set in X . Then $g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A) - A$ does not contain any nonempty π -closed set.

Proof. Let F be a nonempty π -closed set such that $F \subset g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A) - A$. Then $F \subset g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A) \cap (X - A) \subset (X - A)$ implies $A \subset X - F$ where $X - F$ is π -open. Therefore $g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A) \subset X - F$ implies $F \subset (g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A))^c$. Now $F \subset g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A) \cap (g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(A))^c$ implies F is empty.

Reverse implication does not hold.

2.12 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$ and let $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, \{a, b\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c, d\}, X\}$. Let $A = \{c\}$ then $g\zeta^*$ - $cl(A) = \{c, d, e\}$, $g\zeta^*$ - $cl(A) - A = \{d, e\}$ does not contain any nonempty regular closed set but A is not $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed set.

2.13 Corollary. Let A be $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed. A is $g\zeta^*$ -closed iff $g\zeta^*$ - $cl(A) - A$ is π -closed.

Proof. Let A be $g\zeta^*$ -closed set then $A = g\zeta^*$ - $cl(A)$ implies $g\zeta^*$ - $cl(A) - A = \emptyset$ which is π -closed.

Conversely, if $g\zeta^*$ - $cl(A) - A$ is π -closed then A is $g\zeta^*$ -closed.

2.14 Theorem. If A is π -open and $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed. Then A is $g\zeta^*$ -closed and hence clopen.

Proof. Let A be regular open. Since A is $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed, $g\zeta^*$ - $cl(A) \subset A$ implies A is $g\zeta^*$ -closed. Hence A is closed. (Since every π -open $g\zeta^*$ -closed set is closed). Therefore A is clopen.

2.15 Theorem. For a space X , the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is extremally disconnected,
- (b) Every subset of X is $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed
- (c) The topology on X generated by $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed set is the discrete one.

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b).

Assume that X is extremally disconnected. Let $A \subset U$ where U is π -open in X . Since U is π -open, it is the finite union of regular open sets and X is extremally disconnected, U is finite union of clopen sets and hence U is clopen. Therefore $g\zeta^*$ - $cl(A) \subset cl(A) \subset cl(U) \subset U$ implies A is $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed.

(b) \Rightarrow (a)

Let A be a regular open set of X . Since A is $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed by **Theorem 2.14**, A is clopen. Hence X is extremally disconnected.

(b) \Leftrightarrow (c) is obvious.

3. $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -open sets

3.1 Definition. A subset A of a space X is called π -generalized $g\zeta^*$ -open (briefly $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -open) iff its complement is $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed set.

3.2 Lemma. If A be a subset of X , then

- (a) $g\zeta^*$ - $cl(X - A) = X - g\zeta^*$ - $int(A)$.
- (b) $g\zeta^*$ - $int(X - A) = X - g\zeta^*$ - $cl(A)$.

3.3 Theorem. A subset A of a space X is $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -open iff $F \subset g\zeta^*$ - $int(A)$ whenever F is π -closed and $F \subset A$.

Proof. Let F be π -closed set such that $F \subset A$. Since $X - A$ is $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed and $X - A \subset X - F$ where $F \subset g\zeta^*$ - $int(A)$. Conversely,

Let $F \subset g\zeta^*$ - $int(A)$ where F is π -closed and $F \subset A$. Since $F \subset A$ and $X - F$ is π -open, $g\zeta^*$ - $cl(X - A) = X -$

$g\zeta^*$ -int(A) \subset X – F. Therefore A is $\pi g\zeta^*$ -open.

3.4 Theorem. If $g\zeta^*$ -int(A) \subset B \subset A and A $\pi g\zeta^*$ -open then B is $\pi g\zeta^*$ -open.

Proof: Since $g\zeta^*$ -int(A) \subset B \subset A, by **Theorem 2.10**, $g\zeta^*$ -cl(X – A) \supset (X – B) implies B is $\pi g\zeta^*$ -open.

3.5 Remark. For any A \subset X, $g\zeta^*$ -int($g\zeta^*$ -cl(A) – A) = \emptyset .

3.6 Theorem. If A \subset X is $\pi g\zeta^*$ -closed then $g\zeta^*$ -cl(A) – A is $\pi g\zeta^*$ -open.

Proof. Let A be $\pi g\zeta^*$ -closed and F be a π -closed set such that F \subset $g\zeta^*$ -cl(A) – A. By **Theorem 2.11**, F = \emptyset

implies F \subset $g\zeta^*$ -int($g\zeta^*$ -cl(A) – A). By **Theorem 3.3**, $g\zeta^*$ -cl(A) – A is $\pi g\zeta^*$ -open.

Converse of the above theorem is not true.

3.7 Example. Let X = {a, b, c} and let $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Let A = {b}. Then A is not $\pi g\zeta^*$ -closed but $g\zeta^*$ -cl(A) – A = {a, b} is $\pi g\zeta^*$ -open.

4. Quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal spaces

4.1 Definition. A space X is said to be **$g\zeta^*$ -normal** [18] (resp. **α -normal** [1]) if for every pair of disjoint closed subsets A, B of X, there exist disjoint $g\zeta^*$ -open (resp. α -open) sets U, V of X such that A \subset U and B \subset V.

4.2 Definition. A space X is said to be **$\pi g\zeta^*$ -normal** [5] (resp. **π -normal** [6], **$\pi\alpha$ -normal** [16]) if for every pair of disjoint closed subsets A, B of X, one of which is π -closed, there exist disjoint $g\zeta^*$ -open (resp. open, α -open) sets U, V of X such that A \subset U and B \subset V.

4.3 Definition. A space X is said to be **quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal** [5] (resp. **quasi normal** [21], **quasi α -normal** [2]) if for every pair of disjoint π -closed subsets H, K of X, there exist disjoint $g\zeta^*$ -open (resp. open, α -open) sets U, V of X such that H \subset U and K \subset V.

4.4 Definition. A space X is said to be **softly $g\zeta^*$ -normal** [5] (resp. **softly normal** [17], **softly α -normal**) if for every pair of disjoint subsets A, B of X, one of which is π -closed and the other is regularly closed, there exist disjoint $g\zeta^*$ -open (resp. open, α -open) sets U, V of X such that A \subset U and B \subset V.

4.5 Definition. A space X is said to be **mildly $g\zeta^*$ -normal** [18] (resp. **mildly-normal** [20], **mildly α -normal** [2]) if for every pair of disjoint regular closed subsets H, K of X, there exist disjoint $g\zeta^*$ -open (resp. open, α -open) sets U, V of X such that H \subset U and K \subset V.

By the definitions stated above, we have the following diagram:

normal \Rightarrow π -normal \Rightarrow quasi-normal \Rightarrow softly normal \Rightarrow mildly-normal

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

4.6 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, \{a, b\}, \{c, d\}, X\}$. The pair of disjoint closed subsets of X are $A = \{a, b\}$ and $B = \{c, d\}$. Also $U = \{a, b\}$ and $V = \{c, d\}$ are open sets such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$. Hence the space X is normal as well as α -normal. It is also $g\zeta^*$ -normal.

4.7 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$. The pair of disjoint closed subsets of X are $A = \{a\}$ and $B = \{c\}$. Also $U = \{a\}$ and $V = \{c\}$ are open sets such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$. Hence the space X is normal as well as α -normal, since every open set is α -open.

4.8 Theorem. For a space X , the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal.
- (b) For every pair of π -open subsets U and V of X whose union is X , there exist $g\zeta^*$ -closed subsets G and H of X such that $G \subset U, H \subset V$ and $G \cup H = X$.
- (c) For any π -closed set A and every π -open set B in X such that $A \subset B$, there exists a $g\zeta^*$ -open subset U of X such that $A \subset U \subset g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(U) \subset B$.
- (d) For every pair of disjoint π -closed subsets A and B of X , there exist $g\zeta^*$ -open subsets U and V of X such that $A \subset U, B \subset V$ and $g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(U) \cap g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(V) = \emptyset$.

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b), (b) \Rightarrow (c), (c) \Rightarrow (d) and (d) \Rightarrow (a).

(a) \Rightarrow (b). Let U and V be any π -open subsets of a quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal space X such that $U \cup V = X$. Then, $X - U$ and $X - V$ are disjoint π -closed subsets of X . By quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normality of X , there exist disjoint $g\zeta^*$ -open subsets U_1 and V_1 of X such that $X - U \subset U_1$ and $X - V \subset V_1$. Let $G = X - U_1$ and $H = X - V_1$. Then, G and H are $g\zeta^*$ -closed subsets of X such that $G \subset U, H \subset V$ and $G \cup H = X$.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). Let A be a π -closed and B is a π -open subsets of X such that $A \subset B$. Then, $X - A$ and B are π -open subsets of X such that $(X - A) \cup B = X$. Then, by part (b), there exist $g\zeta^*$ -closed sets G and H of X such that $G \subset (X - A), H \subset B$ and $G \cup H = X$. Then, $A \subset (X - G), (X - B) \subset (X - H)$ and $(X - G) \cap (X - H) = \emptyset$. Let $U = X - G$ and $V = (X - H)$. Then U and V are disjoint $g\zeta^*$ -open sets such that $A \subset U \subset X - V \subset B$. Since $X - V$ is $g\zeta^*$ -closed, then we have $g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(U) \subset (X - V)$. Thus, $A \subset U \subset g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(U) \subset B$.

(c) \Rightarrow (d). Let A and B be any disjoint π -closed subset of X . Then $A \subset X - B$, where $X - B$ is π -open. By the part (c), there exists a $g\zeta^*$ -open subset U of X such that $A \subset U \subset g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(U) \subset X - B$. Let $V = X - g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(U)$. Then, V is a $g\zeta^*$ -open subset of X . Thus, we obtain $A \subset U, B \subset V$ and $g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(U) \cap g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(V) = \emptyset$.

(d) \Rightarrow (a). It is obvious.

4.9 Proposition. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function, then:

- (a) The image of $g\zeta^*$ -open subset under an open continuous function is $g\zeta^*$ -open.
- (b) The inverse image of $g\zeta^*$ -open (resp. $g\zeta^*$ -closed) subset under an open continuous function is $g\zeta^*$ -open (resp. $g\zeta^*$ -closed) subset.
- (c) The image of $g\zeta^*$ -closed subset under an open and a closed continuous surjective function is $g\zeta^*$ -open.

4.10 Theorem. The image of a quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal space under an open continuous injective function is a quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal.

Proof. Let X be a quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal space and let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an open continuous injective function. We need to show that $f(X)$ is a quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal. Let A and B be any two disjoint π -closed sets in $f(X)$. Since the inverse image of a π -closed set under an open continuous function is a π -closed. Then, $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are disjoint π -closed sets in X . By quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normality of X , there exist $g\zeta^*$ -open subsets U and V of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$, $f^{-1}(B) \subset V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$. Since f is an open continuous injective function, we have $A \subset f(U)$, $B \subset f(V)$ and $f(U) \cap f(V) = \emptyset$. By **Proposition 4.9**, we obtain $f(U)$ and $f(V)$ are disjoint $g\zeta^*$ -open sets in $f(X)$ such that $A \subset f(U)$ and $B \subset f(V)$. Hence $f(X)$ is quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal.

From the above theorem, we have the following corollary.

4.11 Corollary. Quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normality is a topological property.

The following lemma helps us to show that quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normality is a hereditary with respect to closed domain subspaces.

4.12 Lemma. Let M be a closed domain subspace of a space X . If A is a $g\zeta^*$ -open set in X , then $A \cap M$ is $g\zeta^*$ -open set in M .

4.13 Theorem. Quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normality is a hereditary with respect to closed domain subspaces.

Proof. Let M be a closed domain subspace of a quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal space X . Let A and B be any disjoint π -closed sets in M . Since M is a closed domain subspace of X , then we have A and B be any disjoint π -closed sets of X . By quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal of X , there exist disjoint $g\zeta^*$ -open subsets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$. By the **Lemma 4.12**, we obtain $U \cap M$ and $V \cap M$ are disjoint $g\zeta^*$ -open sets in M such that $A \subset U \cap M$ and $B \subset V \cap M$. Hence, M is quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal subspace.

Since every closed and open (clopen) subset is a closed domain, then we have the following corollary.

4.14 Corollary. Quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normality is a hereditary with respect to clopen subspaces.

The following result is useful for giving some other characterizations of quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal spaces.

4.15 Theorem. For a space X , the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal.

- (b) For any disjoint π -closed sets H and K , there exist disjoint $gg\zeta^*$ -open sets U and V such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$
- (c) For any disjoint π -closed sets H and K , there exist disjoint $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -open sets U and V such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.
- (d) For any π -closed set H and any π -open set V containing H , there exists a $gg\zeta^*$ -open set U of X such that $H \subset U \subset g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(U) \subset V$.
- (e) For any π -closed set H and any π -open set V containing H , there exists a $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -open set U of X such that $H \subset U \subset g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(U) \subset V$.

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b), (b) \Rightarrow (c), (c) \Rightarrow (d), (d) \Rightarrow (e) and (e) \Rightarrow (a).

(a) \Rightarrow (b). Let X be quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal space. Let H, K be disjoint π -closed sets of X . By assumption, there exist disjoint $g\zeta^*$ -open sets U, V such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$. Since every $g\zeta^*$ -open set is $gg\zeta^*$ -open, U and V are $gg\zeta^*$ -open sets such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). Let H, K be two disjoint π -closed sets. By assumption, there exist disjoint $gg\zeta^*$ -open sets U and V such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$. Since $gg\zeta^*$ -open set is $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -open, U and V are $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -open sets such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

(c) \Rightarrow (d). Let H be any π -closed set and V be any π -open set containing H . By assumption, there exist disjoint $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -open sets U and W such that $H \subset U$ and $X - V \subset W$. By **Theorem 3.3**, we get $X - V \subset g\zeta^*\text{-int}(W)$ and $g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(U) \cap g\zeta^*\text{-int}(W) = \emptyset$. Hence $H \subset U \subset g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(U) \subset X - g\zeta^*\text{-int}(W) \subset V$.

(d) \Rightarrow (e). Let H be any π -closed set and V be any π -open set containing H . By assumption, there exist $gg\zeta^*$ -open set U of X such that $H \subset U \subset g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(U) \subset V$. Since, every $gg\zeta^*$ -open set is $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -open, there exists $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -open sets U of X such that $H \subset U \subset g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(U) \subset V$.

(e) \Rightarrow (a). Let H, K be any two disjoint π -closed sets of X . Then $H \subset X - K$ and $X - K$ is π -open. By assumption, there exists $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -open set G of X such that $H \subset G \subset g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(G) \subset X - K$. Put $U = g\zeta^*\text{-int}(G)$, $V = X - g\zeta^*\text{-cl}(G)$. Then U and V are disjoint $g\zeta^*$ -open sets of X such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

5. Preservation Theorems

5.1 Definition. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be

- (a) **$g\zeta^*$ -closed [8]** (resp. **$\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed**) if $f(F)$ is $g\zeta^*$ -closed (resp. $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed) in Y for every closed set F of X .
- (b) **rc-preserving [14]** (resp. **almost closed [19], almost $g\zeta^*$ -closed, almost $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed**) if $f(F)$ is regular closed (resp. closed, $g\zeta^*$ -closed, $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed) in Y for every $F \in RC(X)$.
- (c) **π -continuous [4]** (resp. **almost π -continuous [4]**) if $f^{-1}(F)$ is π -closed in X for every closed (resp. regular closed) set F of Y .
- (d) **almost continuous [19]** if $f^{-1}(V)$ is open in X for every regular open set V of Y .
- (e) **$\pi gg\zeta^*$ -continuous** (resp. **almost $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -continuous**) if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $\pi gg\zeta^*$ -closed in X for every closed (resp. regular closed) set F of Y .

5.2 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost π -continuous and $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed function, then $f(A)$ is $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed in Y for every $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed set A of X .

Proof. Let A be any $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed set of X and V be any π -open set of Y containing $f(A)$. Since f is almost π -continuous, $f^{-1}(V)$ is π -open in X and $A \subset f^{-1}(V)$. Therefore, we have $g \zeta^* \text{-cl}(A) \subset f^{-1}(V)$ and hence $f(g \zeta^* \text{-cl}(A)) \subset V$. Since f is $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed, $f(g \zeta^* \text{-cl}(A))$ is $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed in Y and hence we obtain $g \zeta^* \text{-cl}(f(A)) \subset g \zeta^* \text{-cl}(f(g \zeta^* \text{-cl}(A))) \subset V$. Hence $f(A)$ is $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed in Y .

5.3 Theorem. A surjection $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is almost $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed if and only if for each subset S of Y and each $U \in \text{RO}(X)$ containing $f^{-1}(S)$, there exists a $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -open set V of Y such that $S \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$.

Proof. Necessity. Suppose that f is almost $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed. Let S be a subset of Y and $U \in \text{RO}(X)$ containing $f^{-1}(S)$. If $V = Y - f(X - U)$, then V is a $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -open set of Y such that $S \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$.

Sufficiency. Let F be any regular closed set of X . Then $f^{-1}(Y - f(F)) \subset (X - F)$ and $(X - F) \in \text{RO}(X)$. There exists a $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -open set V of Y such that $Y - f(F) \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset (X - F)$. Therefore, we have $f(F) \supset (Y - V)$ and $F \subset X - f^{-1}(V) \subset f^{-1}(Y - V)$. Hence we obtain $f(F) = Y - V$ and $f(F)$ is $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed in Y , which shows that f is almost $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed.

5.4 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -continuous, rc-preserving injection and Y is quasi $g \zeta^*$ -normal, then X is quasi $g \zeta^*$ -normal.

Proof. Let A and B be any disjoint π -closed sets of X . Since f is an rc-preserving injection, $f(A)$ and $f(B)$ are disjoint π -closed sets of Y . Since Y is quasi $g \zeta^*$ -normal, there exist disjoint $g \zeta^*$ -open sets U and V of Y such that $f(A) \subset U$ and $f(B) \subset V$.

Now if $G = \text{int}(\text{cl}(U))$ and $H = \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$. Then G and H are regular open sets such that $f(A) \subset G$ and $f(B) \subset H$. Since f is almost $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -continuous, $f^{-1}(G)$ and $f^{-1}(H)$ are disjoint $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -open sets containing A and B , respectively. It follows from **Theorem 4.15**, that X is quasi $g \zeta^*$ -normal.

5.5 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a π -continuous, almost $g \zeta^*$ -closed surjection and X is quasi $g \zeta^*$ -normal space then Y is $g \zeta^*$ -normal.

Proof. Let A and B be any two disjoint closed sets of Y . Then $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are disjoint π -closed sets of X . Since X is quasi $g \zeta^*$ -normal, there exist disjoint $g \zeta^*$ -open sets U and V such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset V$.

Let $G = \text{int}(\text{cl}(U))$ and $H = \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$. Then G and H are disjoint regular open sets of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset H$. Now, we set $K = Y - f(X - G)$ and $L = Y - f(X - H)$. Then K and L are $g \zeta^*$ -open sets of Y such that $A \subset K$, $B \subset L$, $f^{-1}(K) \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(L) \subset H$. Since G and H are disjoint, so are K and L . Since K and L are $g \zeta^*$ -open and we obtain $A \subset g \zeta^* \text{-int}(K)$, $B \subset g \zeta^* \text{-int}(L)$ and $g \zeta^* \text{-int}(K) \cap g \zeta^* \text{-int}(L) = \emptyset$. Therefore, Y is $g \zeta^*$ -normal.

5.6 Theorem. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an almost π -continuous and almost $\pi g g \zeta^*$ -closed surjection. If X is quasi $g \zeta^*$ -normal space then Y is quasi $g \zeta^*$ -normal.

Proof. Let A and B be any disjoint π -closed sets of Y . Since f is almost π -continuous, $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are disjoint π -closed sets of X . Since X is quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal, there exist disjoint $g\zeta^*$ -open sets U and V of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset V$.

Put $G = \text{int}(\text{cl}(U))$ and $H = \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$. Then G and H are disjoint regular open sets of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset H$. By **Theorem 5.3**, there exist $\pi g\zeta^*$ -open sets K and L of Y such that $A \subset K$, $B \subset L$, $f^{-1}(K) \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(L) \subset H$. Since G and H are disjoint, so are K and L by **Theorem 3.3**, $A \subset g\zeta^*\text{-int}(K)$, $B \subset g\zeta^*\text{-int}(L)$ and $g\zeta^*\text{-int}(K) \cap g\zeta^*\text{-int}(L) = \emptyset$. Therefore, Y is quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal.

5.7 Corollary. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost continuous and almost closed surjection and X is a normal space, then Y is quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal.

Proof. Since every almost closed function is almost $\pi g\zeta^*$ -closed. Therefore, by **Theorem 5.6**, Y is quasi $g\zeta^*$ -normal.

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